

PRESERVATION OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBERS AFTER MULTIPLE PYROLYSIS CYCLES

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RESEARCH QUESTIONS

WE CAN RECYCLE CF $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{How many times?} \\ \text{At what cost in performance?} \end{array} \right.$

WE CAN IMPROVE RECYCLING \longrightarrow More effective? Faster?

METHODOLOGY

Pyrolysis and consecutive **oxidation** is performed in a furnace with controlled atmosphere and gas flow. Two **distinctive methods** are used. Each method is applied up to three times, **every consecutive** treatment is a **cycle**.

CF Porcher 12K + Epoxy LY1564 =

Model composite!

Method	T (°C)	Pyrolysis t (min)	Oxidation t (min)	Total t (min)
Rapid (R)	550	5	10	15
Slow (S)	500	30	30	60

RESULTS

Single fiber tensile tests are performed to evaluate effect of the recycling cycles on properties of CF.

CONCLUSIONS

- **Rapid** method favours **stiffness** retention, while **slow** method holds **strength** better.
- Above **95%** retention on stiffness after **two** cycles.
- **Third cycle** shows drastic drop of mechanical properties, specially for the rapid method.

This project is within the **CREATERNITY** Graduate School at LTU

